

THE ANALYSIS OF INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC RELATIONS BETWEEN UZBEKISTAN AND THE USA

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Annotation: *The article analyzes economic relations between Uzbekistan and the United States. The analysis of the state of attraction of foreign investments in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the investment climate and the country's investment attractiveness are studied. Conclusions and proposals have been developed to further improve the investment policy of Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *US companies operating in Uzbekistan, investment climate, investment policy, investment quality, positive effects of attracting foreign investment, shortcomings of attracting foreign direct investment, improving investment policy .*

The Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021, adopted on the initiative of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, aims to further increase the effectiveness of reforms in the country, create the necessary conditions for comprehensive and systematic development of the state and society. the fifth direction of the Action Strategy, which has been widely discussed, is related to foreign policy and foreign economic activity. All its directions are aimed, first of all, at creating decent living conditions for the people, further enhancing the image of our country in the world community, raising the image of Uzbekistan in the world media, as well as ensuring peace and stability and security. The concept of foreign policy of the country, developed by the First President Islam Karimov and fully meeting democratic requirements and international standards, is being continued at a new stage by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev. , one of the priorities of our foreign policy is to strengthen cooperation with the United States. Uzbek-American relations are characterized by their comprehensiveness, integrity, longevity and versatility. At the same time, it is based on universally recognized principles of international law, in

particular, mutual respect and consideration of each other's interests. Uzbekistan and the United States share a common position on a number of international and regional issues. Particular attention should be paid to cooperation in the field of regional and global security threats, in particular, the fight against drug trafficking, the proliferation of weapons of mass destruction, as well as the strengthening of peace and stability in Central Asia and Afghanistan. is focused. The Declaration on the Foundations of Strategic Partnership and Cooperation, signed in March 2002, is a key document that sets out to establish qualitatively new and mutually beneficial relations in all areas of Uzbek-American relations. A comprehensive "Roadmap" for the development of mutually beneficial cooperation with the United States is being implemented in order to strengthen bilateral cooperation and timely implementation of these agreements.

It should be noted that Shavkat Mirziyoyev and Donald Trump took office almost simultaneously, and since then relations between the two countries have been gradually intensifying.

Delegations at various levels have changed in the recent past. The heads of state met in Riyadh in May 2017 and in New York in September. During a telephone conversation in December, Donald Trump invited Shavkat Mirziyoyev to pay an official visit to the United States. This, of course, means that the reforms being carried out by the Uzbek leader are being recognized internationally. On May 16, 2018, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev was received at the White House by President of the United States Donald Trump.

In his address to the Oliy Majlis on the most important priorities for 2019, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev said: billion dollars. Today, 456 projects worth \$ 23 billion are being implemented in our country at the expense of foreign investments. ”

The U.S. leader supports President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's reform agenda and recognizes Uzbekistan's growing role as an economic leader. During the high-level talks, Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted that Uzbekistan is seeking membership in the World Trade Organization. President Trump said the United States would provide technical assistance to Uzbekistan in implementing reforms to liberalize its trade regime in accordance with the organization's norms. The issues of intensification of contacts between the ministries and companies and business circles of the two countries, the implementation of joint investment projects in high technology, trade and industry, fuel and energy, transport and other areas are constantly being discussed.

However, it should be noted that despite the introduction of the most-favored-nation treatment in trade, the volume of bilateral trade is not as high as it could be. In 2017, for example, the figure was just over \$ 210 million. In the first eight months of 2018, the figure was 300 million. Yes, there is growth. However, we are convinced that the economy of a country as developed as the United States and as advanced as Uzbekistan is in fact capable of much more.

Leading U.S. companies are currently operating in Uzbekistan. In particular, General Motors Power Plant Uzbekistan is engaged in the production of engines for passenger cars with the participation of General Motors Corporation. In addition, Boeing has become a regular partner of Uzbekistan Airways, supplying modern aircraft, in particular, the new generation of Boeing-787-8 Dreamliner.

General Electric Corporation is an important partner of Uzbekistan in the oil and gas and aviation sectors, as well as in the development of health and renewable energy sources.

In addition, U.S. companies operating in Uzbekistan include Exxon Mobil, CNH Industrial, Coca-Cola, Hyatt, Hilton, John Deere, Honeywell, and Caterpillar. and others. The opening of a branch of Webster University in Tashkent has further strengthened international relations between the two countries.

"President Mirziyoyev has promised to create a favorable environment for business in Uzbekistan and open its markets to U.S. companies and investors," the White House said in a statement. Uzbekistan and the United States have signed more than 20 major contracts worth \$ 4.8 billion (38 trillion Uzbek soums) if fully implemented.

The number of jobs created as a result has not yet been calculated, but some American companies have announced new projects. On May 15, Jizzakh Petroleum of Uzbekistan and Honeywell UOP of the United States signed licensing and engineering contracts for the construction of an oil refinery in Jizzakh region, which will process 5 million tons of oil per year.

On May 16, US General Electric announced that it had signed a contract with Uzbekenergo to build a 660-megawatt unit at the Tashkent Thermal Power Plant.

During Mirziyoyev's visit, the Uzbek Foreign Trade Ministry signed various agreements with American partners.

In particular, the US company WCC International has agreed to implement a joint project to ensure uninterrupted access of Uzbek products to the US market. The plan is to promote such products on electronic platforms, especially on Amazon.

"We have made some progress in this regard," Uzbek Foreign Trade Minister Jamshid Khodjaev said in a May 17 statement. "We are currently negotiating with Amazon's management and drafting a memorandum."

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